

EFFECT OF SOIL AMENDMENTS ON GROWTH, YIELD AND NUTRITIONAL QUALITY OF JUTE (*CORCHORUS OLITORIUS*) LEAVES IN THE FOREST-SAVANNA TRANSITIONAL ZONE OF GHANA

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Abstract

The study was conducted from March to July, 2024 at the Multipurpose Crop Nursery of the Akenten Appiah-Menka University of Skills Training and Entrepreneurial Development, Mampong campus to evaluate the growth, yield and nutritional quality response of Jute leaves (*Corchorus olitorius*) to different soil amendments. A Randomized Complete Block Design with six treatments and three replications was used for the study. The six treatments were; No amendment (Control), 10 t ha⁻¹ Chicken manure (CM), 20 t ha⁻¹ CM, 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPK, 400 kg ha⁻¹ NPK and 10 t ha⁻¹ CM + 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPK. The results showed that the different soil amendments did not significantly ($P \geq 0.05$) influence plant height, number of leaves per plant and leaf area from 14 to 28 DAP. Plants that received 20 t ha⁻¹ CM followed by 10 t ha⁻¹ CM produced significantly taller plants and higher number of leaves per plant than plants grown on the unamended plots as well as plants that received 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPK from 42 DAP to 70 DAP. The 10 t ha⁻¹ CM + 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPK and 20 t ha⁻¹ CM produced the widest leaf area at 42 and 70 DAP respectively and was significantly wider than the control at the same period. Amending soil with 20 t ha⁻¹ CM produced the highest yield, mineral content (Ca, Fe and K) and higher ash content, total carbohydrate, crude fibre, crude protein and moisture content as compared to the control. The study recommends the application of 20 t ha⁻¹ CM for optimum yield and nutritional content of *Corchorus olitorius*.

Keywords: Jute Leaves, Nutritional Quality, Proximate Composition, *Corchorus Olitorius*, Chicken Manure.

Introduction

Jute leaves (*Corchorus olitorius*), commonly known as Ayoyo in Ghana, are an important leafy vegetable valued for their high nutritional and medicinal benefits. Rich in essential vitamins and minerals—such as vitamins A, C, E, iron, and calcium—jute leaves contribute significantly to dietary health, particularly in communities within the Northern Savannah zone of Ghana (Alege *et al.*, 2025). Beyond nutrition, *C. olitorius* also yields eco-friendly fiber, contributing to soil conservation and climate mitigation. Despite their nutritional potential and economic value, especially in fiber production, jute remains underutilized and stigmatized in urban areas, often

associated with poverty (Bakare-Odunola *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, its cultivation faces major constraints due to soil degradation and overreliance on costly inorganic fertilizers (Purbajanti *et al.*, 2019). Organic alternatives like poultry manure have been shown to enhance soil fertility and improve crop performance across various vegetable species, including okra, ginger, and cucumber. However, limited research has been conducted in Ghana on the effect of chicken manure on jute mallow. This study therefore aims to determine the optimal rate of chicken manure and NPK fertilizer application that can significantly enhance the growth, yield, and nutritional quality of *Corchorus olitorius*.

Methodology

The field experiment was conducted from March to July 2024 at the Multipurpose Crop Nursery of AAMUSTED. Mampong (7° 8' N, 1° 24' W) is located in Ghana's Forest-Savannah Transitional Zone. A Randomized Complete Block Design with six treatments and three replications was used. Treatments included: No amendment (Control), 10 t ha⁻¹ Chicken manure (CM), 20 t ha⁻¹ CM, 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPK, 400 kg ha⁻¹ NPK and 10 t ha⁻¹ CM + 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPK. *Corchorus olitorius* seeds obtained from CSIR-Crops Research Institute were sown in rows at a spacing of 30 cm × 20 cm and thinned at one week after sowing. Soil, manure and jute leaves samples were taken for routine analysis. Cultural practices such as weeding, watering, and pest control (using Ronfos insecticide) were implemented. The chicken manure was air-dried and decomposed for two weeks and applied two weeks before sowing, while NPK obtained from Kyeiwaa Agrochemical shop was applied using the side placement one week after thinning. Data was collected biweekly from 14 to 70 DAP and analyzed using ANOVA in GenStat 18.1. Treatment means were separated using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) at a 5% significance level.

Results

The application of chicken manure (CM) significantly improved soil chemical properties compared to unamended plots. The highest soil pH, available P, total N, and exchangeable bases were observed under 20 t/ha CM, while 10 t/ha CM led in organic carbon (OC) and organic matter (OM) content. Although early growth (14–28 DAP) showed no significant differences, 20 t/ha CM resulted in the tallest plants and widest leaf area from 42–70 DAP, significantly outperforming NPK and control treatments. Leaf number peaked under 10 t/ha CM and 10 t/ha CM + 200 kg/ha NPK. Yield was highest with 20 t/ha CM (870 kg/ha), which surpassed all other treatments, including the control (145 kg/ha). Mineral and

proximate composition of jute leaves improved significantly with CM application, with 20 t/ha CM yielding the highest Ca, Fe, K, ash, crude protein, and moisture content. Strong positive correlations were found between plant height and leaf area ($r = 0.84$), calcium and iron ($r = 0.70$), and crude protein and yield ($r = 0.70$).

Application of 20 t/ha CM significantly improved soil pH, nutrient availability (N, P, K), and organic matter content compared to inorganic fertilizers and the control. This enhanced soil fertility promoted better vegetative growth, with taller plants, more leaves, and larger leaf areas observed from 42 to 70 DAP. This agrees with the findings of Atakora *et al.* (2025). Yield was highest under 20 t/ha CM (870 kg/ha), followed by 10 t/ha CM, both outperforming NPK treatments. The combination of 10 t/ha CM + 200 kg/ha NPK also produced higher yields than sole NPK or the control. Strong positive correlations were observed between plant height, leaf area, yield, and crude protein. Additionally, plants treated with 20 t/ha CM had significantly higher mineral and proximate contents, indicating improved nutritional quality of *Corchorus olitorius*. Organic amendments, especially chicken manure, proved more effective than inorganic fertilizers in enhancing soil fertility, plant growth, yield, and leaf nutrient content. Similarly, Agbede (2025) found that 10 t/ha of chicken manure significantly improved maize yield, soil fertility, and mineral content over the control.

Conclusion

The study found that applying 20 t/ha chicken manure significantly improved soil fertility, growth, yield, and nutritional quality of *Corchorus olitorius* hence recommended for optimal productivity, while 10 t/ha CM + 200 kg/ha NPK is a viable alternative where resources are limited.

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Fig. 1. Plant height as influenced by soil amendments

Fig. 2. Number of leaves as influenced by soil amendments

Fig. 3. Leaf area as influenced by soil amendments

Table 1: Yield of *Corchorus olitorius* as influenced by different soil amendments

Treatment	Yield (kg /ha)
No amendment (Control)	145.00e
10 t /ha ² CM	606.00b
20 t /ha ² CM	870.00a
200 kg /ha ² NPK	244.00d
400 kg /ha ² NPK	166.33e
10 t /ha ² CM + 200 kg /ha ² NPK	566.33c
LSD (P≤0.05)	39.60
CV (%)	5.03

Values followed by the same letters under a column are not significantly different at P=0.05; LSD= Least significant difference; CV (%) = Coefficient of variation

Fig. 4. Proximate and nutritional properties of jute mallow leaves influenced by soil amendments